

Material Suplementar

Título do Trabalho: O Papel dos Sistemas de Drones na Entrega de Desfibriladores Externos Automáticos e sua Influência no Tempo-Resposta em Paradas Cardíacas Extra-Hospitalares: Uma Revisão Integrativa

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Evento: I Congresso PROFURG de Tecnologias em Saúde e V Simpósio de Gestão, Tecnologia e Inovação em Urgência e Emergência, 2025

Conteúdo: Lista completa de referências bibliográficas (N=30) citadas no resumo expandido.

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